

CHEMICAL SCIENCES

RESEARCH OF HYDROCARBON-BASED DRILLING SOLUTIONS

Abdullayeva K.

assistant PhD in Chemistry

Hasanova N.

assistant

Azerbaijan State Oil and Industry University, Baku, Azerbaijan

Abstract

Drilling mud is a multicomponent, dispersed colloidal system with specific physical and chemical properties. It is important to dispose of drilling mud. Hydrocarbon-based drilling mud was taken as the object of research. Mineral oils "VMGZ" and "I-5A" were used as hydrocarbon-based drilling mud, and synthetic oil "SHELLSOL" was used for comparison. These oils were treated with asphalt-resin additives. During the research, the viscosities of these oils before and after treatment with additives were analysed at different temperatures. As the temperature increased, a decrease in viscosity was observed.

Keywords: drilling fluid, disposal, mineral oil, synthetic oil, asphalt-resin, viscosity, temperature.

Introduction

In recent years, two trends have emerged in the global oil and gas industry:

1. Increase well throughput through improved oil and gas production technologies in developed and new fields;

2. Development of deposits which were not previously exploited due to geological, technological, climatic, and environmental conditions.

In order to implement these trends in well construction, it is necessary to construct wells with a large inclination angle, multi-faceted and large horizontal tip to increase oil and gas production. In this case, the type and quality of the drilling fluid play an important role[1]. One of the reasons for the low productivity of wells is the use of water-based drilling fluids. Because when using these fluids, the fluid filtrates enter the pore space of the formation and the oil is pushed back, the clay cement of the formation swells, compounds insoluble with reagents, and water-oil emulsions are formed. Emulsion drilling fluids can provide the required quality drilling process. This allows maintaining the permeability of the bottom zone of the formation, eliminating tool hardening, ensuring the stability of wells, and removing cuttings. However, it has been proven that emulsion drilling fluids, along with their advantages, have a number of disadvantages [2].

Especially when drilling high-temperature wells, with an increase in temperature, rheological properties decrease and intensive evaporation of their components occurs. The research method for improving the technology of hydrocarbon-based drilling fluids for drilling high-temperature wells is relevant and requires study. The use of hydrocarbon-based drilling fluids in drilling operations increases the efficiency of opening productive layers.

The basis of emulsion drilling fluid is a hydrocarbon fluid, which determines its physico-chemical and technological properties. The most common of these are the following:

1. oil refining products, gas condensate, oil, diesel fuel, mineral oils

2. petrochemical synthesis products based on plant and animal raw materials - olefins, their oligomers, linear alkylbenzenes, polyolefins, acetals, ethers, synthetic oils.

The use of diesel fuel as a hydrocarbon-based drilling fluid is limited by environmental fire requirements. Synthetic oils are mainly used in offshore projects where the use of biodegradable fluids is mandatory. However, in onshore drilling, mineral oils from various manufacturers are most often used. Mineral oil is the main fluid for emulsion solutions, is a petroleum product, is formed from the distillation of fuel oil and has a high degree of variability. Mineral oils are a complex colloidal system which consisting of high molecular weight compounds (asphaltenes, resins, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons, paraffins) and low molecular weight hydrocarbons of different qualities and composition[3].

Two main types of waste are generated during drilling operations: produced water and drilling waste. Waste drilling fluids contain harmful substances such as chemical additives, clay, and oil. With the purpose preventing of used drilling fluids from affecting the environment and people, they should be properly managed. That is why their disposal is an important issue.

Experimental part

During the research, oils from various manufacturers can be used as hydrocarbon fluids: "AKS 5/10" (Halliburton company), off-season thickened hydraulic oil "VMGZ" (Schlumberger company), industrial oil "I-5A" (ISK PetroEngineering), and synthetic oil "SHELLSOLL" (Netherlands). The main characteristics of the oils are as follows:

- kinematic viscosity
- density
- flash point
- freezing temperature
- viscosity index
- alkalinity number (not always indicated)
- acid number (not always shown)

Table 1.

Technical characteristics of the researched oils				
Features	"AKS" 5/10	"VMGZ"	"I-5A"	"SHELLSOL"
20 °C, kg/m ³	895	868	872	793
Kinematic viscosity, mm ² /sec	8.7 (40 °C)	9 (50 °C)	6.5-8.2 (40 °C)	1.98 (15 °C)
Flash point (open cup), °C	+92	+133	+122	+97
Freezing temperature, °C	-14	-62	-14	-
Acid value, mg KOH/g oil	-	0.3-0.9	0.03	-
Alkalinity value, mg KOH/g oil	-	-	-	-
Viscosity index	-	158	-	-
Mass fraction of sulfur, %	-	-	-	-
Water content, %	0.04	no	no	-
Mechanical impurities content, %	0.007	no	no	-

In our research, we used "VMGZ", "I-5A", and "SHELLSOL" oils. The viscosity values of these oils were tested at different temperatures.

Table 2.

Plastic viscosity values of oils at various temperatures (without additives)

Temperature	"VMGZ"	"I-5A"	"SHELLSOL"
0 °C	10	26	3
20 °C	5	8	2
50 °C	4	5	1
70 °C	2	2	1
90 °C	1	1	1

Figure 1. Temperature dependence of the plastic viscosity of oils at different temperatures (without additives)

Without additives, the viscosity of oils decreases with increasing temperature. At 0 °C, the viscosity of

"I-5A" oil is superior to other oils. At 90 °C, the viscosity of "I-5A" oil decreased by 26 times compared to 0 °C. At 90 °C, the viscosity of all 3 oils is equal to 1.

Fig 2. Viscosimeter FANN

Then the oils were treated with asphalt-resin compounds. "VMGZ" oil produced by Schlumberger was treated with "VERSATROL". "VERSATROL" is a natural asphalt (gilsonite). "I-5A" oil from ISK "Petro-Engineering" was treated with EWO Block. For comparison, "SHELLSOL" synthetic oil was treated with "BARATROL" additive. "BARATROL" is a modified hydrocarbon. During the research, the first concentra-

tion was taken as 10 kg/m^3 , and the second concentration was taken as 20 kg/m^3 . To maximize the hydrocarbon dispersion of the samples, they were mixed in a Hamilton Beach laboratory mixer for 4 hours. Then, the plastic viscosity of the oils was checked at temperatures of 0, 20, 50, 70, 90 °C using a 6-stage FANN viscosimeter (Fig. 2) and a thermocouple.

Table 3.

Plastic viscosity values of "VMGZ" oil treated with "VERSATROL" at different temperatures

Name	Concentration	"VMGZ"				
		0 °C	20 °C	50 °C	70 °C	90 °C
VERSATROL	10 kg / m ³	15	8	4	3	2
	20 kg / m ³	15	6	5	2	1

Figure 3. Temperature dependence of the viscosity of "VMGZ" oil after treatment with the "VERSATROL" additive

Table 4.

Plastic viscosity values of “I-5A” oil processed with “EWO Block” at different temperatures

Name	Concentration	“I-5A”				
		0 °C	20 °C	50 °C	70 °C	90 °C
EWO Block	10 kg / m3	44	13	5	2	2
	20 kg / m3	44	11	4	1	2

Versus temperature after treatment with “EWO Block” additive

Table 5.

Plastic viscosity values of SHELLSOL synthetic oil treated with BARATROL at different temperatures

Name	Concentration	"SHELLSOL"				
		0 °C	20 °C	50 °C	70 °C	90 °C
BARATROL	10 kg / m3	4	3	2	1	1
	20 kg / m3	3	2	1	1	1

Figure 4. Temperature dependence of the viscosity of “SHELLSOL” synthetic oil after treatment with the “BARATROL” additive

Conclusion

The viscosity of the oils was checked depending on the temperature. According to the results of the research, a decrease in viscosity was observed in the oils “VMGZ”, “I-5A”, “SHELLSOL” with an increase in concentration and temperature both before and after treatment with asphalt-resin additives. However, the viscosity after treatment is higher than before treatment. More changes were noticeable in the oil “I-5A”. The results in the synthetic oil “SHELLSOL” are almost stable.

References

1. Tiron Denis Vyacheslavovich. Technological improvement of emulsion solutions for drilling wells in

conditions of higher bottom hole temperatures. Dissertation competition for the academic degree of candidate of technical sciences. Ukhta-2017.

2. Abdul Razak Ismail, Abdul Come on. Alias, Wan Rosli Wan Sulaiman, Mohd. Zaidi Jaafar, Issham Ismail. Drilling fluid waste management in drilling for oil and gas wells. Chemical engineering transactions, vol.56, page-1351, 2017.

3. Dianjie Sui, Mingwang Zhan, Dianxue Sui and Fulei Zhao. Regulations and methods for disposal of waste drilling fluid. IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science 631, page-1, 2021.